

METHODS OF MODIFICATION OF POLYOLEFINS BASED ON MINERAL FILLERS.

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Abstract: In this article, the literature on polypropylene modified with vermiculite mineral filler composites was studied and a new type of polypropylene composite material was synthesized. The ultraviolet analysis method of the synthesized composite material was studied.

Keywords: Polypropylene, catalyst, composite, ultraviolet, polymerization, polyolefin.

Polyolefins, including polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS), are widely used plastics in our daily lives. Overuse and improper handling of plastics lead to significant environmental pollution as well as energy waste. Biodegradation of polyolefins appears to be an environmentally friendly and low-energy method for plastic degradation. Many strains that can degrade polyolefins have been isolated from the environment. Some enzymes have also been identified with the function of polyolefin degradation. With the development of synthetic biology and metabolic engineering strategies, the engineered strains could be used to degrade plastics [1.79-90.b].

This paper reviews the major discoveries that have played a major role in the polyolefin field and have established polyolefins as the most widely produced plastic. The development of polyolefins, including the production of LDPE (low density polyethylene) at ICI (Imperial Chemical Industries) and the discovery of Phillips or Ziegler-Natta catalysts, are highlighted in the first section. The second section discusses the impact of the use of molecular catalysts on polyolefin research, along with the latest advances leading to highly efficient custom-made resins. [2.2-6.b].

According to F. Christakopoulos et al., polyolefins are semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymers known for their good mechanical properties, low manufacturing costs, and chemical resistance. They are one of the most widely used plastics, and many polyolefin grades are considered engineering polymers. Polyolefins, such as polypropylene and polyethylene, can in principle be processed by both methods. However, the semi-crystalline nature of polyolefins

complicates the application of additive manufacturing methods compared to amorphous polymers. First, the crystallization process leads to severe shrinkage during cooling, and the processing temperature and cooling rate affect the mechanical properties and mesoscopic structure of the manufactured parts. [3.249-256.b].

The unprecedented growth and socio-economic impact of polyolefins clearly demonstrate a great success story in the world of polymer science. Polyolefins are revolutionizing industries such as healthcare, construction, and food packaging. Despite the advantages of polyolefins, there is growing concern for the environment due to their high production volume (i.e., fossil fuel consumption), often short lifespan, and issues related to waste management and accumulation in the natural environment. Creating a circular economy for polyolefins through efficient recycling technologies has the potential to reduce the environmental impact of these materials. This perspective discusses polyolefins and their impacts, existing and emerging recycling/recycling solutions, and recycling alternatives that challenge the status quo.[4.519-530.b]

Current recycling technologies rarely achieve 100% pure plastic fractions from a single polymer type. Often, sorted batches containing a single polymer type actually contain small amounts of other polymers as contaminants. This inevitably affects the properties of the recycled plastic.[5.312-324.b].

The material properties of the single films, as well as the electrical performance of test modules using these different encapsulants, were studied. The different films exhibit comparable optical, thermal, and thermo-mechanical properties with only minor differences in UV transparency and melting temperature. [6.1277-1288.b].

In recent decades, the use of engineering plastics, especially polyolefins, has increased significantly, mainly due to their low cost, good mechanical properties and light weight. However, this increase in use has also brought about many problems related to disposal and their environmental impact. This is because polyolefins do not decompose easily in the natural environment, and therefore the need for biodegradable polyolefins has become a major research topic. [7.1015-1049.b].

Polyolefins, the world's largest commodity plastics, are widely used in many industries. As representatives of the chemical processing of polyolefin waste into fuels and bulk fine chemicals, polyolefin catalytic cracking and hydrocracking based on zeolite or metal zeolite composite catalysts are the most

effective routes due to their large capacity and strong adaptability to existing petrochemical equipment. [8.1482-1491.b].

Figure 1. Changes in the physical and mechanical properties of organo-inorganic polymer materials based on mineral fillers and polypropylene PP under the influence of UV rays with a wavelength of 290-320 nm at a constant temperature (25 °C).

Thus, according to the results of the research, highly filled organic polymer materials have high performance properties, resistant to low temperatures and ultraviolet rays, and can be recommended for use in the production of products for various purposes (in particular, in the production of pipes) and in extreme weather conditions.

The table shows that the change in the flexural strength and impact resistance properties of vermiculite-filled polypropylene (PP)-based organic polymer materials under the influence of ultraviolet rays is less than 20%. In the original unfilled polymers, a decrease in their properties is observed.

Table 1.

Polypropylene (PP)-based polymer filled with vermiculite is an organic polymer.

Composition composition	Impact resistance, kJ/m ²		Bending resistance, MPa	
	UB until radiation	UB after radiation	UB until radiation	UB after radiation
PP	60	42	34	22
PP /VK	56	55	45	41

The impact strength decreased from 60 to 42 kJ/m² in the original polymer, and from 81 to 78 kJ/m² in the PP/PEMA/TEAS/BT composite. It can be seen that the basalt-containing PP-based composite retained 90% of its basic properties after UV irradiation. It can be seen that the impact strength of the PP/VK composites decreased from 70 to 60 kJ/m² and from 78 to 66 kJ/m², respectively, after UV irradiation. It was observed that the impact strength of the PP/VT composite decreased from 79 to 66 kJ/m² after UV irradiation. Studies have shown that the absorption of UV radiation by organic polymer materials leads to the destruction of their polymer chains and a decrease in their strength properties. The degree of polymer chain destruction increases with increasing irradiation time, especially in unfilled polymers.

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